

BRAND Front-end Cryogenic Noise Measurements at Yebes. Polarization #1.

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A	2019-07-17	All	First Issue
B	2019-12-02	Title, Section 2	Subtitle added to distinguish it from the second polarization chain measurements. Added notch filter frequency data from the manufacturer. Corrected a typo in the filter losses of the second paragraph in section 5.
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1. Introduction

The receiver for BRAND-EVN¹ RadioNet4 Joint Research Activity shall cover a one decade bandwidth from 1.5 to 15.5 GHz, which will be directly digitized. Its front-end comprise (1) horn, (2) polarizer², (3) coupler for the injection of phase and noise calibration signals, (4) highpass filter to reject lower than 1.5 GHz interferences, (5) notch filter tuned to two in-band interfering frequencies and (6) balanced low noise amplifier [1].

Prior to the final assembly of the receiver, it was required to have a realistic estimation of the noise performance of the front-end and to dismiss any unexpected or undesired consequences of the combination of all elements. However, the project Dewar was not finished yet and the available cryostats were not big enough to include the horn and allow for noise measurements using external hot and cold loads. A reasonable alternative was to measure only the coupler, filters and amplifier using the cold attenuator method, which is well established in the Yebes Observatory test setup.

Additionally, being the filters and coupler superconducting, it was considered very convenient to have an independent measure of its cryogenic performance, especially of the insertion loss, which is very difficult to obtain with enough accuracy by direct cryogenic S-parameter measurements. These losses can be easily derived from the noise contribution of each element placed at the input of the cryogenic amplifier.

To attain these goals a set of measurements in the 1.5-15.5 GHz band were planned using Yebes Observatory noise measurement system 1020-3, the same in which the BRAND amplifiers were characterized. This report describes the measurement procedures and the different setups used and displays and analyzes the results of the measurements and the estimations of the losses.

2. Superconducting components data

We include here as a reference the information received from the manufacturer of the coupler and the filters. Only the data corresponding to the units used is presented.

The serial number of the units measured is 190-4A02³.

The highpass filter specified cutoff frequency is 1.5 GHz.

The rejection frequencies for the notch filter as specified in [4] are 1.83-1.86 GHz and 2.11-2.17 GHz. The manufacturer measures rejection >23 dB @ (1.813,1.835) and >18 dB @ (2.106,2.147).

¹ Broad Band European VLBI Network.

² The use of a polarizer is still TBD. Another possibility is to convert linear to circular polarization once the signal is digitized. We have not included a polarizer in these measurements.

³ Surprisingly, there is a common serial number for all units. The different units can be distinguished by the labels Notch Filter, Highpass Filter, Coupler. There is another set for the other polarization with serial number 190-4A01

Note the coupler poor return loss above 10.5 GHz and coupling factor above 11.5 GHz (figure 3). A new improved coupler is being designed.

Figure 1: Notch filter response data measured by the manufacturer.

Figure 2: Highpass filter response data measured by the manufacturer.

Figure 3: Coupler response data measured by the manufacturer.

3. Measurement considerations

3.1. Measurement procedures

The superconducting elements and the whole front-end chain are characterized measuring its noise temperature (and gain) placed at the input of one of the low noise balanced amplifiers build for BRAND receiver. The balanced amplifier is comprised of two 3 dB quadrature hybrid couplers and two low noise amplifiers. A report describing this LNA and its performance can be found in [2].

System 1020-3 is a 12 K Dewar implementing the cold attenuator noise measurement method [3]. A HP N8975A noise figure meter was used in combination with an Agilent N4002A noise source, and an in-house-built 15 dB attenuator specially designed in a m-GaAs substrate for broadband cryogenic operation and accurate temperature readings (see figure 5). This system brings the possibility of measuring cryogenic S parameters simultaneously, but with less accuracy, as the cold attenuator is in the signal path (see Appendix).

Note that the cold attenuator used in the measurements presented in [2] is not the same as the one in use during the present tests. As a result of the system update and recalibration, **an offset of ≈ 1 K has appeared in the noise results** (noise data is now 1 K higher, for the noise temperature range of these tests). Its origin is under investigation. It is not relevant for the purpose of these tests, as we are aiming at relative measurements only. **Absolute noise data should be used with caution until this discrepancy is solved.**

To calculate the loss of the element(s) placed in front of the LNA from the noise measurements we use the simplified expression (1) in which we assume a perfect matching at the amplifier input. We can neglect mismatching effects as the input reflection of the balanced LNA is lower than -20 dB in most of the band.

$$L_{DUT} = 10 \log \left(\frac{T_{DUT} + T_{eq\ LNA+DUT}}{T_{DUT} + T_{eq\ LNA}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where L_{DUT} and T_{DUT} represent the loss and the physical temperature of the element(s) at the input of the LNA (DUT), while $T_{eq\ LNA}$ and $T_{eq\ LNA+DUT}$ are the noise temperatures of the LNA alone and the LNA with the DUT at its input.

3.2. Measurement setup

Follows a list of the different setups measured. In view of the bad behavior of the coupler, the measurement of the complete chain (setup 2) was repeated without the coupler (setup 3).

1. Reference measurement of the balanced LNA
2. Complete chain: Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + U-cable + LNA
3. Complete chain excluding the Coupler: Highpass filter + Notch filter + U-cable + LNA
4. Notch filter: Notch filter + LNA
5. Highpass filter: Highpass filter + LNA
6. Verification measurement of the balanced LNA

Special care is taken to ensure that the measurements are comparable, as small errors could easily be attributed to the DUT noise contribution. The noise temperature of the LNA is

measured before and after the batch of tests to check that the calibration has not changed and we use a consistent reference value in the determination of the losses of the superconducting components. The physical temperature of the LNA has a small impact in the noise temperature. For a conventional LNA this is not very significant (less than 0.1 K per K for this noise temperature range) but in this particular case of a balanced amplifier, the influence of the temperature of the input hybrid – non superconducting – is important. As the temperature of the aluminum cold plate of the 1020-3 Dewar is not homogeneous, the temperature of the DUTs can change between cool-downs if its position shifts or the thermal path to the cold plate is modified. Temperature sensors are placed in each DUT, the cold attenuator and reference locations in the 12 K and 50 K stages of the Dewar. Cooling brackets and copper braids have been tailored to each DUT and setup to guarantee repetitive temperatures in all cool-downs.

A **“U” cable** had to be inserted between the LNA input and the other components in setups 2 and 3, because the complete chain line is longer than the length of the Dewar. It is an extremely short (4 cm) and low loss $\varnothing.141$ in copper cable (see Fig. 4) with an estimated average loss at 15 K lower than 0.1 dB. Its contribution has not been subtracted from the results of setups 2 and 3. Its impact in the ripple is minimal, as the input reflection of the balanced amplifier is very good. **Male to male SMA transitions** have also been used when needed to interconnect the DUTs with female connectors. Its contribution has not been subtracted either. It has been possible to avoid the use of right angle transitions, with usually poor reflection characteristics. The output of the LNA is connected to the stainless steel access line by a low loss flexible cable, which is not relevant for the comparisons, as its effect is negligible and equal for all the setups.

Figure 4: *Low loss “U” cable used in setups 2 and 3. Length is approximately 4 cm.*

A schematic of the setup including all components is represented in figures 5 and 6. The other schematics of the other setups would be similar (excluding from the DUT only the elements not being measured). Photographs of the different setups are shown in the next section, where the details specified above can be seen.

Figure 5: Simplified schematic of the noise measurement system1020-3, implementing the cold attenuator method. The elements used for simultaneous S parameter measurements have been omitted for clarity.

Figure 6: Example of the DUT of the previous figure corresponding to setup #2 (all elements). Represents the arrangement of figure 9 (here input is on the left). Note that when referring to DUT in the text we often exclude the LNA.

We have used the **balanced amplifier** with LNAs Y214G 1014 and 1015 and hybrids YH90214 3021 and 3023. All measurements have been obtained with the LNAs in the nominal operating conditions stated in [2]. The bias settings are shown in table 1.

LNAs BIAS SETTINGS			
Stage	#1	#2	#3
Drain Voltage (V)	2.8	1.3	3.0
Drain current (mA)	12	5	15
Gate Voltage (V)	0.04	-0.16	-0.11

Table 1: Bias settings of both amplifiers used in all the measurements presented.

4. Results

Table 2 reflects the temperature of the different components of each measurement setup.

SENSOR TEMPERATURE IN K (LNA ON)

Setup	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6
50 K plate ref.	62.48	61.90	61.30	62.90	61.5	64.07
12 K plate ref.	16.81	16.82	17.13	17.03	16.65	17.18
Cold attenuator	16.45	16.62	16.98	16.52	16.17	16.81
LNA	15.91	16.22	16.02	15.92	15.59	16.04
Input hybrid	12.50	12.87	12.65	12.46	12.14	12.57
Notch filter	-	17.09	14.50	15.77	-	-
Highpass filter	-	15.87	14.43	-	15.26	-
Coupler	-	12.65	-	-	-	-

Table 2: Readings of the temperature sensors used in the different setups.

For each measurement configuration we present a graph comparing the noise and gain of the set measured with the noise and gain of the balanced LNA. Frequency resolution is generally 200 MHz. Details of some plots were measured with finer resolution (50 MHz or 20 MHz) and displayed independently.

Another plot represents the loss of the DUT in two curves, one calculated from the noise increment due to the DUT using (1) and another, less accurate, subtracting the gain of the LNA and the gain of the set, resulting from the Y factor measurements. A linear fit to the loss curve derived from the noise measurements is also presented in the plot.

The average value in the band of the loss for each DUT is presented in the following table. These values do not represent the superconducting losses only, as they include non-idealities in the response of the DUTs, transitions, connectors and the “U” cable, depending on the setup.

	ΔT_{eq} ($T_{eq,DUT+LNA} - T_{eq,LNA}$)	L (from ΔT_{eq})	L (from ΔG)
Highpass filter	1.00	0.17	(0.18)
Notch filter	0.91	0.15	(0.20)
Highpass+Notch filters	2.13	0.37	(0.33)
Coupler+Highpass+Notch filter	4.10	0.64	(0.71)

Table 3: Average loss in the band for the *different setups estimated from noise measurements with the LNA (eq. (1)) and from gain difference (less accurate, in brackets). The average for the set including the coupler is only between 1.5 and 11.5 GHz.*

4.1. Setup #1: Amplifier reference measurement

Figure 7: Setup 1&6 – Balanced amplifier reference measurement. Input and cold attenuator are on the right.

Figure 8: Balanced amplifier noise and gain reference measurement. The noise measurements taken at the beginning and end of the campaign differ on average in 0.1 K.

4.2.Setup #2: Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + LNA

Figure 9: Setup 2 – Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable + Balanced amplifier. Input and cold attenuator are on the right. The two male to male SMA transitions are included in the results.

Figure 10: Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable + Balanced amplifier noise and gain compared to balanced amplifier alone, revealing the bad behavior of the coupler above 11.5 GHz. Lower frequency resolution (0.5 GHz) was used in this case.

Figure 11: Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable loss. In green, the estimation from noise measurements. In red, the linear fit of the green curve. In blue, a direct loss calculation from the gain obtained in the noise measurement. Lower frequency resolution (0.5 GHz) was used in this case. Average loss from noise measurements (up to 11.5 GHz) is **0.64 dB**.

4.3.Setup #3: Highpass filter + Notch filter + LNA

Figure 12: Setup 3 – Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable + Balanced amplifier. Input and cold attenuator are on the right. The male to male SMA transition is included in the results.

Figure 13: Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable + Balanced amplifier noise and gain compared to balanced amplifier alone. Note the various features introduced by the filters, best viewed in the figures corresponding to each filter.

Figure 14: Highpass filter + Notch filter + “U” cable loss. In green, the estimation from noise measurement (notches are excluded). In red, the linear fit of the green curve. In blue, a direct loss calculation from the gain obtained in the noise measurement. Average loss in the band from noise measurements (without notches) is **0.37 dB**.

4.4.Setup #4: Highpass filter + LNA

Figure 15: Setup 4 – Highpass filter + Balanced amplifier. Input and cold attenuator are on the right. Another amplifier is being tested in the Dewar. The male to male SMA transition is included in the results.

Figure 16: Highpass filter + Balanced amplifier noise and gain compared to balanced amplifier alone. The difference is quite uniform apart from the dip around 1.75 GHz, enlarged in the next figure.

Figure 17: Detail from the previous figure of the high noise contribution of the highpass filter between 1.5 and 2 GHz due to the ripple of its transfer function close to the cutoff frequency.

Figure 18: Highpass filter loss. In green, the estimation from noise measurements. In red, the linear fit of the green curve. In blue, a direct loss calculation from the gain obtained in the noise measurement. Average loss in the band from noise measurements is **0.17 dB**.

4.5.Setup #5: Notch filter + LNA

Figure 19: Setup 5 – Notch filter + Balanced amplifier. Input and cold attenuator are on the right. The male to male SMA transition is included in the results.

Figure 20: Notch filter + Balanced amplifier noise and gain compared to balanced amplifier alone. Some of the bumps in noise temperature produced by the irregular response of the notch filter are zoomed in the following figures. Only one notch is resolved with this frequency sampling; the next figure shows both.

Figure 21: Detail of the notches from the previous figure. Vertical orange lines signal the specified notch stopbands. Note the shift in the lower notch and the bandwidth really affected by the noise degradation of the notches.

Figure 22: Detail of the main noise bump produced by the poor passband response of the notch filter.

Figure 23: Detail of a noise bump produced by the poor passband response of the notch filter.

Figure 24: Notch filter loss. In green the estimation from noise measurements. In red, the linear fit of the green curve. In blue a direct loss calculation from the gain obtained in the noise measurement. Average loss in the band from noise measurements is **0.15 dB**. Only the notches frequencies have been eliminated from the linear regression and average calculation.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

- The complete chain of coupler, filters and balanced amplifier has been successfully measured at 15 K. No major new problems were detected in the assembled receiver chain. Despite the use of the “U” cable and the non-ideal reflection coefficient of some

of the components, the noise ripples are quite low and significant comparisons between the amplifier noise and the noise with the different components at the input could be made.

- The results are coherent. The losses of the superconducting elements are very low, taking into account the SMA connectors and transitions included in the measurements: around 0.15 dB for each filter module plus male to male transition. It is possible to check that the sum of the loss of the two filters measured individually ($0.15+0.17=0.32$ dB) minus the loss of the two filters measured together (0.37 dB) is 0.05 dB, which accounts for the cryogenic losses of the miniature “U” cable minus the extra male to male adapter used in the joint measurement.
- The repeatability of the measurements is very good (0.1 K average difference between the LNA measurements at the beginning and end of the campaign) and the stability of the measurement system and the temperature of the LNA and DUTs in the different arrangements guarantees comparable results.
- The need of male to male transitions increments the loss, size and complexity of the system. It would be better to equip the filters, coupler and all components intended to be connected between them directly without cables, with SMA male connectors at the output (and keep the female ones at the input).
- The coupler is not usable above 11.5 GHz (losses are greater than 3 dB). A new one is being designed to correct this problem. It will also have a higher coupling factor to minimize the contribution of the room temperature noise through the coupled port.
- The highpass filter response shows a significant ripple in the band near the cutoff frequency (1.55-2 GHz), which nearly doubles the noise temperature at its peak (see figure 17). An improvement in the filter design would greatly benefit the performance of the system in this part of the band, which has required a great effort in the development of the front-end components. If RFI allow, a relaxation of the cutoff frequency specifications could facilitate a new design.
- The stop bands of the notch filter affect a band clearly wider than the specification (see figure 21). The notch specified between 1.83 and 1.86 GHz is also shifted down around 30 MHz.
- The response of the notch filter in the passband presents some bumps at several frequencies probably related with the notches, which degrade the noise temperature of the system. The main ones are between 9-11 GHz and 14-14.5 GHz with a noise temperature increment of around 20% (figures 22 and 23).

References

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Appendix: S-parameter measurements

Figure 25 shows the S parameters of the different arrangements measured in the noise setup with the cryogenic attenuator at the input. A time domain gating has been applied to S11 and S22 to reduce the gain and phase variations at the input attenuator, stainless steel lines and flexible cable when cooled down. However, the results still present ripples; they are useful mainly to detect issues and compare setups.

The data of the balanced amplifier alone is not included here. Good return loss measurements are available in [2].

Figure 25: S parameters measured with noise attenuator at the input of (a) Coupler + Highpass filter + Notch filter + U-cable + LNA (b) Highpass filter + Notch filter + U-cable + LNA (c) Notch filter + LNA (d) Highpass filter + LNA.